

Further Studies on the Determination of Activation Energy of the Thermal Decomposition of Precipitated Magnesium Hydroxide from Dynamic Thermogravimetry

S. B. KANUNGO

Regional Research Laboratory, Bhubaneswar-4, Orissa

Manuscript received 27 September 1973; revised 2 April 1974; accepted 23 September 1974

The values of activation energy for the thermal dehydroxylation of various samples of precipitated magnesium hydroxide have been determined from thermogravimetry (TG) and differential thermogravimetry (DTG) under dynamic condition using three different methods viz., (i) Horowitz and Metzger, (ii) Coats and Redfern and (iii) deviation from DTG trace. Although method (ii) gives two straight lines having different slopes, methods (i) and (iii) give consistent results which are comparable to many of the published work. The sharp change in slope with method (ii) has been explained with the help of a recent theory of proton transfer by tunnelling mechanism.

IN an earlier paper¹ it has been shown that activation energy (E) value of the thermal decomposition of magnesium hydroxide can be determined from TG curve assuming that at any instant during uniform rate of heating i.e., when time co-ordinate is fixed the following rate equation holds good²

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = f(\alpha)Z \exp(-E/RT) \quad (1)$$

when $f(\alpha) = (1-\alpha)^n$ and all the symbols having their usual significances. It has also been shown from Horowitz and Metzger method³ that the order of the reaction is around unity so that

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = (1-\alpha) Z \exp(-E/RT) \quad \dots (2)$$

or

$$\frac{dw}{dT} = (w_\infty - w)Z \exp(-E/RT) \quad \dots (3)$$

when w = weight loss at any instant and w_∞ = final weight loss.

The values of E obtained by the above method agreed in most cases with those obtained from DTA traces by applying Piloyan *et al.*⁴ method. The values of E obtained from equation (3) varied from 52-72 kcal/mole whereas those obtained from DTA traces varied from 46 to 57 kcal/mole depending on the mode of preparation of the samples. However, most of the activation energy values from both the methods were within the range of 52-57 kcal/mole which conform closely with the published⁵ values

for the thermal dehydroxylation of precipitated magnesium hydroxide in air.

Since the publication of the above results the author's attention has been drawn to two recent papers⁶⁻⁷ on the thermal decomposition of magnesium hydroxide. In one of them Girgis⁶ obtained widely differing values of activation energy (38-71 kcal/mole) from isothermal and conventional DTA traces for the same sample by applying various theoretical equations developed by different authors from time to time. In a subsequent paper, Sharp⁷ observed that these results (obtained by Girgis⁶) are of little value if the dynamic methods using DTA traces fail to give reproducible and consistent data. He also observed that the kinetics of thermal dehydroxylation of magnesium hydroxide are strongly dependent on the ambient water vapour pressure which retards the rate of decomposition and therefore, activation energy should be determined at controlled vapour pressure of water (p_{H_2O}). This conclusion was arrived from the much higher values of E obtained from dynamic thermal conditions than those obtained from isothermal weight loss under vacuum. While this observation is quite true regarding the elucidation of the mechanism of decomposition but as far as the practical application of the calcination of magnesium hydroxide is concerned, activation energy obtained under dynamic condition in air is more important than isothermal decomposition *in vacuo*. In this respect, kinetic analysis obtained from TG curves might give useful information as some objection has already been raised by Sharp⁷ to the use of DTA traces. The present paper deals with the determination of activation energy of the thermal dehydroxylation of various samples of magnesium hydroxide precipitated under different conditions, from dynamic thermogravimetry in air.

Experimental

Eleven samples of magnesium hydroxide were prepared and their thermograms were taken according to the procedure described in detail in the previous communication.¹

Results and Discussion

It has already been stated¹ that the applicability of Freeman and Carroll's⁸ equation to the decomposition of magnesium hydroxide is very poor as observed from highly scattered plots. Therefore, an attempt has been made to apply the method (I) developed by Horowitz and Metzger³ who have shown that for thermal decomposition of solid within a certain range of temperature ($T - T_s$) the following relationships hold good:

$$1 - C^{1-n} = (1-n)\exp(E\theta/RT_s^2) \quad \dots (4)$$

and when $n = 1$

$$\ln(1/C) = \exp(E\theta/RT_s^2) \quad \dots (5)$$

where C = solid concentration at any instant expressed in mole fraction;

T_s = temperature at the maximum rate of decomposition ($^{\circ}\text{K}$);

$\theta = T - T_s$, when $T(^{\circ}\text{K})$ is the temperature at any instant.

Fig. 1.

T_s can be easily found out as it is the temperature of maximum inflection in TG curve or in a better way maximum in DTG curve. The reaction order n is related to the concentration of substance (C_s) capable of decomposition at the maximum rate of decomposition in the following way

$$C_s = (n)^{1-n} \quad \dots (6)$$

Figs. 1 and 2 show the plot of logarithm of the left hand side ($\log Y$) of either equation (4) or (5) vs. θ depending on the value of n . While for most of the samples linear relationships passing through the origin are obtained within the range of temperature ($T - T_s$), few samples show somewhat scattered plots i.e., follow the equations (4) and (5) for a small range of temperature. However, the E values obtained from the average lines are shown in Table 1. For most of the samples the range of activation energy value is 43-50 kcal/mole whereas sample nos. 2 and 8 show higher value (≈ 58 kcal/mole) and sample no. 10 shows lower value (≈ 39 kcal/mole).

Coats and Redfern⁹ derived two integrated form of equations (method II) for the study of the kinetics

Fig. 2.

Figs. 1 and 2: Horowitz and Metzger plot for different samples of magnesium hydroxide.

$$\log Y = \log \frac{1 - C^{1-n}}{1-n} \text{ or } \log(1n 1/C) \text{ according as } n \neq 1 \text{ or } n = 1 \text{ respectively.}$$

of solid-state decomposition from TG curves under dynamic condition. For a decomposition when $n \neq 1$ they have shown that

$$\log \left[\frac{1-(1-\alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)T^2} \right] = \log \frac{ZR}{qE} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right] - \frac{E}{2.303RT} \dots (7)$$

and when $n = 1$

$$\log \left[-\frac{\ln(1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right] = \log \frac{ZR}{qE} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right] - \frac{E}{2.303RT} \dots (8)$$

where

α = fraction decomposed, $\frac{\text{weight loss at any instant}}{\text{final weight loss}}$,

q = rate of heating, °C/min.

Thus a plot of left-hand side (log Z) of either equation (7) or (8) vs. $1/T$ should result in a straight line for correct value of n . Since there is theoretical justification for order of reaction 0, 1/2, 1/3, 2/3, and 1 only in solid-state kinetics⁹⁻¹⁰ it is possible to substitute these values into equations (7) or (8) to obtain a best linear fit for wide range of decomposition. All these values for n were tested with sample 1 (figure not shown). It was observed that no single value of n could characterise the complete range of decomposition. Therefore, equations (7) and (8) have been applied to all the samples using the values of n obtained by the Horowitz and Metzger method.

Figures 3 and 4 show the plot of $\log(Z)$ vs. $1/T$ for different magnesium hydroxide samples. For sample nos. 3, 4, 7, 8 and 9 sharp changes in the slopes of the curves are observed within the range of decomposition studied ($\alpha = 0.1-0.7$), showing different values of E (cf. Table 1). Other samples also would have shown similar behaviour if the plots

TABLE I—ACTIVATION ENERGY (E) VALUES* OBTAINED FROM THREE DIFFERENT METHODS FOR THE THERMAL DEHYDRATION OF VARIOUS MAGNESIUM HYDROXIDE SAMPLES

Sl. No. of samples	Horowitz and Metzger (Method I) E, kcal/mole	Coats and Redfern (Method II) E, kcal/mole	DTG trace (Method III) E, kcal/mole
1.	47.5	45.6	61.6
2.	58.0	52.4	57.0
3.	43.0	22.8(82.1)	43.8
4.	45.5	22.8(47.4)	44.3
5.	43.5	42.0	45.6
6.	50.4	45.6	50.2
7.	—	43.3(61.6)	68.0
8.	44.0	16.0(43.3)	57.5(34.2)
9.	43.0	27.4(51.5)	53.8
10.	38.7	37.5	45.6
11.	58.0	—	45.6

* Values in parentheses were obtained from the linear portions after the break.

were made at lower temperatures. The portion of the curve after the initial break corresponds to the

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

Figs. 3 and 4 : Graphical representation of Coats and Redfern equations for different samples of magnesium hydroxide

$$\log Z = \log \left[\frac{1-(1-\alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)T^2} \right] \text{ or } \log \left[-\frac{\ln(1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right] \text{ according as } n \neq 1 \text{ or } n = 1 \text{ respectively.}$$

major decomposition zone of the TG curves for most of the samples.

From the above two methods for the determination of activation energy it is clear that suitable value of the order of reaction (n) must be known before applying the appropriate equation. This is a serious disadvantage especially for method II which does not propose any suitable relationship for the determination of n . Besides, various authors¹⁰⁻¹¹ have questioned the significance of n in determining the kinetic parameters of solid-state reactions especially those controlled by diffusion phenomenon. Therefore, in order to avoid this difficulty a simple method has been used to determine the value of activation energy from differential thermogravimetric (DTG) curve.

Piloyan *et al.*⁴ have earlier shown that by plotting the logarithm of deviation of DTA trace from the base line against the reciprocal of corresponding temperature ($^{\circ}\text{K}$) a linear relationship is obtained, from the slope of which activation energy of any thermal change can be obtained. Applying a similar argument that the area bounded by the DTG trace is proportional to the total loss (or gain) of a substance due to thermal effect the following relationship (Method III) can be obtained at first approximation :

$$\log(h) = C - E/2.303RT \quad \dots (9)$$

where, (h) = deviation of DTG trace from base line (mm);

C = constant.

Since TG curves are mostly taken at constant rate of heating the base line of DTG curve is either time or temperature so that (h) is proportional to either $d\alpha/dt$ or $d\alpha/dT$. This method has been used by some authors¹²⁻¹³ for determining the activation energy of solid-state reaction. Fig. 5 shows a typical model for obtaining h from a derivatogram. The plot of $\log(h)$ against $1/T$ for various magnesium hydroxide samples is shown in Fig. 6. The activation energy values obtained from the slopes of the linear portions are in good agreement with those obtained from methods I and II. The major advantage of this method is that prior knowledge of the order of reaction is not necessary for the determination of E . It is therefore, suggested that inspite of any shortcomings of the method from theoretical stand point it can be used for determining the activation energy of solid-state decomposition.

From Table 1 it is observed that activation energy values of the thermal decomposition of magnesium hydroxide although depends on the mode of precipitation, no definite conclusion can be obtained from these studies. Values obtained from method I agree well with those obtained from method III upto sample no. 6 while for sample nos. 8-11 values obtained from methods I and II conform more closely. Weber and Roy¹⁴ obtained the activation energy value of 46-50 kcal/mole for the thermal dehydration of brucite carried out under known

vapour pressure of water. This range is in good agreement with most of the values in Table 1 although the present values are obtained from thermal

Fig. 5 : A typical derivatogram showing the method for obtaining the deviation (h) from base line of DTG trace with corresponding temperature.

Fig. 6 : Application of equation (9) for the evaluation of activation energy from DTG trace.

decomposition in air. This indicates that for determining the activation energy of a thermal decomposition process control of ambient atmospheric condition

is not very essential as pointed out by Sharp.⁷ The present values also agree well with those reported in the previous communication.¹

The reason for sharp changes in the slopes for some samples in Figs. 3 and 4 is intriguing as far as the thermal decomposition of magnesium hydroxide is concerned. The existence of intermediate form of periclase (MgO) with a 'spinel' like structure resulting from cation migration during dehydration as proposed by Ball and Taylor¹⁵ from X-ray diffraction data and also by Brindley¹⁶ has been questioned by Brett and Anderson¹⁷ who have attributed the presence of intermediate 'spinel' to the presence of impurities. The possibility that a small quantity of very fine particles included in the samples was undergoing dehydroxylation before coarser particles also has been rejected by Weber and Roy¹⁴ on the ground that such phenomenon was not observed with the thermal dehydroxylation of kaolinite and serpentine although the present author feels that this idea should not be totally ruled out until further investigation. The small difference in the heat content or free energy of formation of magnesium oxide from brucite crystals of different crystallographic dimensions¹⁸ cannot lead to such sharp change in the slopes especially in the present investigation where large sample size was used.¹ However, this may be explained from the recent theory put forward by Freund¹⁹⁻²⁰ for the thermal dehydroxylation of magnesium hydroxide.

According to Freund¹⁹ and Nagrl and Freund²⁰ at lower temperature broadening of O-H band in i.r. spectrum at about 300° is due to the commencement of OH-OH interaction at the surface of crystals. Proton transfer by a tunnelling mechanism is then supposed to occur between the adjacent hydroxyl groups followed by removal of water molecules by diffusion. Tunnelling can take place with low activation energy because the energy levels of two OH groups overlap, but at higher temperature where widely spaced OH groups exist higher activation energy is required for jumping of protons to higher energy levels.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Dr. T. P. Prasad, Scientist, for the use of MOM-Derivatograph.

References

1. S. B. KANUNGO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 162.
2. V. M. GORBACHEV and V. A. LOGVINENKO, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1972, **4**, 475.
3. H. HOROWITZ and G. METZGER, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 1464.
4. G. O. PILOYAN, I. D. RAYBCHIKOV and D. S. NOVIKOVA, *Nature*, 1966, **212** (No. 5067), 1229.
5. R. C. TURNER, I. HOFFMAN and D. CHEN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1963, **41**, 243.
6. B. S. GIRGIS, *Trans. Brit. Ceram. Soc.*, 1972, **71**, 177.
7. J. H. SHARP, *Trans. Brit. Ceram. Soc.*, 1973, **72**, 21.
8. E. S. FREEMAN and B. CAROLL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 394.
9. A. W. COATS and J. P. REDFERN, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 68.
10. J. H. SHARP, G. W. BRINDLEY and B. N. N. ACHAR, *Proceedings of the Internat. Clay Conferences, Jerusalem (Israel) 1966*, Vol 1, p. 67.
11. G. W. BRINDLEY, J. H. SHARP, J. H. PATTERSON and B. N. N. ACHAR, *Amer. Mineral.* 1967, **52**, 201.
12. A. A. FOTIEV and V. V. MOCHALOV, *Russian J. Inorg. Chem.* (English Transl.), 1968, **13**, 1636.
13. E. K. BELEYAEV and V. F. ANNOPOLOSKII, *Russian J. Inorg. Chem.* (English Transl.), 1971, **16**, 1723.
14. J. N. WEBER and R. ROY, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1965, **263**, 668.
15. M. C. BALL and H. F. W. TAYLOR, *Mineralog. Mag.*, 1961, **32**, 754.
16. G. W. BRINDLEY, "Progress in Ceramic Science", Pergamon Press, 1963, Vol. 3, p. 1.
17. N. H. BRETT and P. J. ANDERSON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 2044.
18. P. B. HOSTETLER, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1963, **261**, 238.
19. F. FREUND, *Angew Chem. (Internat. Edn.)*, 1965, **4**, 445.
20. H. NAGERL and F. FREUND, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1970, **2**, 387.